

Multilayer photonic integration platform for free space optics - Data Management Plan

Version 0

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Multilayer photonic
integration platform for
free space optics/ No
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Researchers

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Organizations

Centre for Nanoscience and Nanotechnology

Datasets

Title: [Project research data](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Research data will be produced, collected and used during the project as the result of two main activities. The first one is the simulation, design and optimization of novel photonic integrated devices, which commonly generate as output data coming from numerical computation. The second source of research data are measurements collected during the laboratory tests of the fabricated devices. The two types of data are complementary, in the sense that allows to both demonstrate the intended functionality of the developed devices as well as to verify if the assumptions and models used during the design phase to describing the underlining physics were sufficiently precise and informative. The gained knowledge at each cycle of design and test constitute a building block for successive optimizations and new device developments.

Secondary, processed data generated by BEAMS will be commonly made publicly available along with paper publications.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

Simulation and measurement data will be generated as a result of the project activities. Data re-use might be considered from time to time to calibrate and validate the models and assumptions made for the device design. In this case, re-use will be limited to data associated to published papers that have passed peer-review (e.g., available as figures in the papers or associated datasets made freely available by the authors).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

Both primary and secondary data will be generated by the project, coming either from simulations and experiments.

Examples of primary data includes electromagnetic fields simulations within the structures under analysis and raw spectral measurements. These data are usually large in size, produced in a very large quantity (because of the multiple attempts and cycles required to properly develop a photonic component), and, in the case of experimental data, embedded in noise and distortions coming from the experimental environment. For these reasons, and considering the fact that the vast majority of these data are only partial results which do not allow to draw definitive conclusions, primary data will not commonly be made publicly available.

Examples of secondary data include simulated and measured efficiency, losses, or spectral bandwidth, obtained by processing primary data. Also secondary data are usually generated in a large quantity because they are necessary to interpret simulations and experiments. They are however commonly small in size and free of noise and distortion, as allowed by commonly accepted practices for data processing in the photonics field. Secondary data corresponding to the accepted version of the developed devices will be made available, typically at the time of paper publication. This will ensure their nature and meaning will be comprehensively described, maximizing re-usability. Secondary data could be made available also without an associated paper, when this will be considered useful for the community.

1.1.5 What is its format?

- AccessData Custom Content Image
- 8-bit ASCII Text

For the largest part, data will be plain text files, csv files or images (e.g., tiff, jpeg, png)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Primary data could range from tens of megabytes to tens of gigabytes. Secondary data are usually a few kilobytes to a few megabytes in size

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data origins are typically numerical simulations and experiments

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- The public
- Industry

Data, especially secondary ones, might be useful to other researchers to re-develop, optimize, ameliorate devices or to realize new ones. They could also be useful to industry to further develop devices are bring them closer to market products. Finally, they could also be useful for educational purposes, to show case the potentiality of integrated photonics and train students, engineers, and researchers.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

Published datasets will be tagged with a unique DOI identifier, the OrcID of the involved researchers (if available) and the Cordis reference number of the BEAMS project.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

At minimum, metadata will include a description of what the data represents (e.g., an optical spectrum) and a reference to the published paper

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Metadata repository
- Linked Open Data
- Other

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Other

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Zenodo is curated by openAIRE

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

BEAMS research data output

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data will be freely available for download through the selected repository.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

There will not be a specified limit date.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

Commonly accessible data formats will be used

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Other

Clear link with the relevant paper(s) will ensure full understanding and possible re-use of the data

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

TBD

Euro

Other

clean, tag, reference, describe, and upload datasets

Direct cost

No direct cost is envisioned at this point to ensure research data output are FAIR, other than that associated to the time spent by the involved researchers to clean, tag, reference, describe, and upload datasets

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Project software](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

New software might be produced during the lifetime of the BEAMS project, mostly for the design and optimization of photonic components.

Implementations of design tools that will be considered sufficiently mature and valuable for the community will be made available as open source code.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

Data will be represented by code developed in languages commonly used by the community, e.g., python or Matlab.

1.1.5 What is its format?

8-bit ASCII Text

Text files

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Commonly less than a few kilobytes per file.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education

The developed code could be useful to other researchers and students to design and optimize photonic components other than those foreseen by the project.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

Published code will be tagged with a unique DOI identifier, the Orcid of the involved researchers (if available) and the Cordis reference number of the BEAMS project.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

At minimum, metadata will include a description of what the code implements and how to use it

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Metadata repository
- Other

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

<https://github.com>

Code will be published on github and linked in Zenodo to make a permanent identifier available

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI will be provided by Zenodo

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

BEAMS design and optimization code

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Code will be freely available for download through the selected repository.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

There will not be a specified limit date.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

Code will be made available in human readable text files.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

TBD

Euro

Other

clean, comment, tag, reference, describe, and upload code

Direct cost

Cost will be associated with researchers time to clean and comment code, upload it, and generate tags, identifiers and descriptions.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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